

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

D4.3: POIESIS branding: logo, aesthetics, website, and social media presence

Author: *Panagiotis Kavouras(NTUA)*

Reviewer: *Serge P.J.M. Horbach(AU)*

Editor: *Costas A. Charitidis (NTUA)*

Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

Lead partner for this deliverable: *National Technical University of Athens*

Disclaimer: This deliverable has not yet been reviewed by the European Commission. Its content might therefore change as a result of the review process.

Deliverable factsheet:

Project Number:	101057253
Project Acronym:	POIESIS
Project Title:	Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science
Title of Deliverable:	POIESIS branding: logo, aesthetics, website, and social media presence
Work Package:	WP4
Due date according to contract:	31 December 2022 (M4)
Actual delivery date:	05 December 2022
Author:	<i>Panagiotis Kavouras (NTUA)</i>
Reviewer:	<i>Serge P.J.M. Horbach (AU)</i>
Editor(s):	<i>Costas A. Charitidis (NTUA)</i>

ABSTRACT:	<p>Any research project's reachout and impact are highly dependent on the quality of dissemination and communication. A necessary condition for POIESIS to be an impactful project is its findings and output to be disseminated and communicated in an optimal way. This is decided by the types of stakeholders that have an interest or/and a stake at POIESIS' findings; so, there is not one-size-fits-all strategy for an optimal dissemination and communication. This is the reason that D4.3 cannot be understood in isolation from D4.2, upon which is heavily based. This deliverable contains the branding of POIESIS that aims at creating a distinct identity of the project's communication and dissemination channels, i.e. social media, website, and presentation templates. The main elements of the branding are the logo, the aesthetics that provide a uniform and aesthetically appealing look.</p>
------------------	--

Keyword List:	Branding, Logo, Aesthetics, Colour palette, Fonts, Branding mood, Communication, Recognisability

Consortium:

	ROLE	NAME	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	AARHUS UNIVERSITY	AU	Denmark
2.	Partner	WISSENSCHAFT IM DIALOG GGMBH	WiD	Germany
3.	Partner	NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS	NTUA	Greece
4.	Partner	INSTITUTO UNIVERSITÁRIO DE LISBOA	ISCTE	Portugal
5.	Partner	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE	CNRS	France
6.	Partner	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	CSIC	Spain
7.	Associated partner	LONDON SCHOOL OF ECONOMICS AND POLITICAL SCIENCE	LSE	UK

Revision history:

VERSION	DATE	Revised by	Reason
0.1	08.11.2022	Panagiotis Kavouras	Preparation of the 1st draft
0.2	09.11.2022	Serge Horbach	Comments on the 1st draft
0.3	25.11.2022	Panagiotis Kavouras	Preparation of the 2nd draft
0.4	27.11.2022	Serge Horbach	Review of the 2nd draft
0.5	29.12.2022	Panagiotis Kavouras	Preparation of the 3rd draft
0.6	30.12.2022	Costas Charitidis	Edits on the 3rd draft
1.0	05.12.2022	Serge Horbach	Submission of the final version

Table of contents

1	Introduction	5
1.1	The POIESIS project	5
1.2	About this deliverable	6
2	POIESIS branding	7
2.1	POIESIS logo	7
2.2	POIESIS colour palette	8
2.3	POIESIS typography	9
2.4	Combination of branding elements	10
3	POIESIS branding in action	11
3.1	POIESIS website	11
3.2	POIESIS social media	14
3.3	POIESIS powerpoint template	15
3.4	POIESIS deliverable template	16
4	Deviations from DoA	17

1 Introduction

1.1 The POIESIS project

In a context where societal dependence on sound scientific research and responsible innovation has become increasingly visible, concerns about public trust and mistrust in science have simultaneously been mounting. Pressing global and local challenges cannot be adequately addressed without reliance on valid evidence and innovation uptake. Hence, the cultural authority of science, research, and innovation – the confidence and trust that citizens and societal actors place in science, research, and innovation – is of crucial importance. The project, entitled “Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science” (POIESIS), will systematically develop a knowledge base about trust in science, including detailed examination of how patterns of trust relate to the alignment of research practices with fundamental principles of research integrity on the one hand and the integration of citizens and societal actors in research practices on the other hand.

POIESIS is concerned with the creation or making of knowledge in responsible ways as well as with the consequences in stages of knowledge utilisation, verification and adoption. We examine research integrity and societal integration as prominent vehicles for responsible knowledge creation. We recognize the obvious intrinsic value of conducting research in accordance with appropriate ethical, legal, and professional frameworks, obligations, and standards on the one hand and with the integration of relevant societal stakeholders in all phases of the research cycle on the other hand. However, we tailor our conceptual and empirical research programme to focus specifically on the impact of such responsible (or irresponsible) research practices in terms of societal trust. Our intention is to systematically examine the impact of research integrity and society’s integration in research on societal trust in research and innovation.

The overarching research objective of POIESIS is to understand how, and to what extent, societal trust in science, research, and innovation is affected by the aligning of research practices with principles of research integrity and by the integration of citizens and societal stakeholders in different phases of the research cycle. Moreover, the project aims to understand how institutions, particularly Research Performing and Research Funding Organisations, can foster research practices that are, in turn, conducive to enhancing public trust in science. Our goal is to develop evidence-based recommendations for tackling societal mistrust and for strengthening the societal co-creation of research; ultimately contributing in the long-term perspective to increased public trust in science and increased alignment of research with societal needs, expectations, and values.

The evidence-base produced by the project will enable us to contribute to the following specific objectives:

1. To provide recommendations for policy makers, research funding and performing organisations, higher education institutions and other R&I actors for tackling societal mistrust in science, research and innovation;
2. To provide recommendations to research performing and funding organisations, for strengthening the co-creation of research and innovation contents by society, and for the spreading of good practices and evidence of their effects; and
3. To implement innovative means of communicating and disseminating the findings and messages of our research.

A core set of general recommendations, relevant for all end-users, will be extended by sets of user-specific recommendations tailored to their needs. All POIESIS recommendations will be packaged together in an accessible and attractive format, tailored to the specific needs of diverse actors, thereby promoting mutual understanding among Research and Innovation stakeholders.

1.2 About this deliverable

POIESIS' conceptual and empirical research will include co-creation with prospective user groups and stakeholders. WP4 will function as the engine for connecting POIESIS with relevant user communities and stakeholders and will catalyse dissemination and uptake of project results. Taking also into account specific objective 3 (section 1.1), the project's dissemination and communication strategy plays a significant role in both recruitment and awareness raising activities. As a result, these activities need to be backed by a powerful branding.

A necessary condition for POIESIS to be an impactful project is its findings and outputsto be disseminated and communicated in an optimal way. This depends onthe types of stakeholders that have an interest and/or a stake in POIESIS' findings; so, there is no one-size-fits-all strategy for optimal dissemination and communication. This is the reason that D4.3 cannot be understood in isolation from D4.2, upon which it is heavily based.

This deliverable contains the branding of POIESIS that aims at creating a distinct identity of the project's communication and dissemination channels, i.e. social media, website, and presentation templates. The main elements of the branding are the logo and the aesthetics that provide a uniform and aesthetically appealing look.

2 POIESIS branding

2.1 POIESIS logo

The POIESIS main logo is presented in Figure 1 and it is a central element of the project; in other words it is the main feature that distinguishes POIESIS from the constellation of other SwafS and WIDERA projects. As a result, it stands as a substantive part of the project's dissemination and communication. It reflects the main concept of POIESIS, described by the Greek word *poiesis*, which has its roots in the ancient Greek «ποίησις». The original Greek meaning of *poiesis* is creating or making. It is related to, but distinct from, the concept of *praxis*, also based in the ancient Greek word «πράξις». Both are about action or agency, but while *praxis* is concerned with and assigns primary value to the action itself, **poiesis focuses on the impact or consequences of the action.**

Figure 1: The POIESIS logo; a well-cut gemstone.

The project's logo is a geometric representation of a well-cut gemstone. This selection reflects the difference between *praxis* and *poiesis*, i.e. the main concept of the project. More specifically, for a gemstone – that is unearthed having a random shape – to be appealing (and valuable as a result) it must be cut through specific crystallographic planes, the so-called “cleavage planes”. Different cuttings can drastically increase or decrease (or even completely destroy) the potential appeal/value of an uncut gemstone. So, the *praxis* of unearthing the gemstone must be followed by the *poiesis* of the cutting, i.e. the creation of a valuable gemstone.

This is, in the consortium's view, a powerful metaphor of the 3i4t (Integrity, Integration, Institutions for Trust) conceptual model, upon which the empirical programme of POIESIS is based. POIESIS will

seek to make visible those positive research practices of integrity and integration (metaphorically, the shiny “cleavage planes”) of science as it is applied in different institutions. This role (metaphorically, the cutting procedure) is taken up by the chains of mediation, that have the crucial role of “exposing” these practices to the public, in order to boost societal trust in science (metaphorically, to increase the appeal/value of the gemstone).

Other variations of the logo have also been presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Variations of the main POIESIS logo.

2.2 POIESIS colour palette

The colour palette of POIESIS is presented in Figure 3. The difference in the area covered by each colour in Figure 3 reflects, in a semi-quantitative way, the prominence these colors are bound to have in all POIESIS’ dissemination and communication channels. The colour palette has been tuned to reflect and produce the “mood” that the POIESIS beneficiaries have chosen for the branding; that is: “Groups of people, engaging, urban sights, portraits, along with hand-drawn elements” (Figure 4).

This mood provides a friendly environment for the end user, by exchanging hand-drawn, cartoon-style elements with blocks of text that provide information on the project (for more details, please

refer to section 3 below). Especially the hand-drawn elements aim at producing an informal atmosphere and enacting a visual leitmotif that creates a sense of unity throughout the dissemination and communication channels of POIESIS.

Figure 3: The colour palette of POIESIS.

Figure 4: The «moodboard» of POIESIS.

2.3 POIESIS typography

Typography plays an important role in communicating an overall tone and quality. Careful use of typography reinforces brand personality and ensures clarity and harmony in all the POIESIS communications. Figure 5 presents a display of the typographic elements that are going to be used in all dissemination and communication activities of the project.

Figure 5: The typography of POIESIS.

2.4 Combination of branding elements

Special guidelines are going to be followed in combining the branding elements of colour palette and typography. Figure 6 gives an overview of these guidelines that aim to provide a combination of optimal clarity of the text and a professional aesthetic result.

Figure 6: Combinations of colour and typography for an optimal result.

3 POIESIS branding in action

This section describes the application of the POIESIS branding in the main dissemination and communication channels of the project, namely the social media, website, as well as powerpoint and deliverable templates.

3.1 POIESIS website

The POIESIS website, upon its launch, will have the domain name poiesis-project.eu. It is going to act as the focal point of the project's online dissemination channels, i.e. Twitter and LinkedIn. More specifically, the project's social media pages will be easily reachable through the website's front page. The design of the website was created during the first two months of the project, in collaboration with the coordinating team. POIESIS' website is going to be launched within December 2022, i.e. a few weeks in advance of the planned-by-the-DoA date (31st of December 2022). Below, we present a series of screen captures from the mock ups of the project's website.

Figure 7: The top of the website's front page. All distinct aesthetic features of the project's branding (logo, colour palette, hand-drawn figure) are visible.

Figure 8: A figure that describes the 3i4t conceptual model will be prominently placed at the front page.

Target groups

Figure 9: All relevant stakeholders will be showcased and described on the front page. For reasons of clarity, the details of each specific stakeholder type will be visible only by hovering over.

Figure 10: A description of the basic objectives of the project will be featured on the front page.

Contact us

Personal information

name / surname email

profession company / organization

subject

Message

type

I'm not a robot

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT
The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101006470.

Figure 11: A standard form for communication will be placed at the bottom of the front page, together with the acknowledgement of our funders.

Our News

12.03.22 [Read More](#)

12.03.22 [Read More](#)

Figure 12: A separate section will feature the news feed.

Figure 13: A separate section will feature the project's deliverables.

The above screen shots depict the initial version of the POIESIS website. As the projects becomes more mature, the progress and results will be featured in specially designed sections. As a result, the website will go through a series of updates, so as to reflect the progress of the POIESIS empirical programme.

3.2 POIESIS social media

The POIESIS social media channels will initially be Twitter and LinkedIn. Twitter is going to be utilised for both dissemination and communication purposes, while LinkedIn is going to be utilised for dissemination purposes. Despite the fact that both platforms do not provide enough flexibility for substantive branding, WP4 leaders have used all available means to customise the mood in both cases. Figure 14 presents the application of POIESIS branding in Twitter (left) and LinkedIn (right). The use and choice of specific social media platforms will be monitored on a continuous basis throughout the project, as to examine the appropriatedness and capacities of the platforms to reach the project's objectives.

Figure 14: POIESIS branding as applied to Twitter (left) and LinkedIn (right) social media platforms. The tweet and post shown here were obtained from the communication of the Kick-off meeting in Aarhus, Denmark on the 8th and 9th of September 2022.

POIESIS' website is going to be hosted on NTUA's server and it will be maintained there for three years after the end of the project, as described in the Grant Agreement. In addition, POIESIS' social media channels will stay active for the same duration of time after the end of the project.

3.3 POIESIS powerpoint template

Figure 15 presents the powerpoint template of POIESIS. This template is specially important, since all presentations related to POIESIS in various occasions (e.g. conferences, workshops, cluster meeting dissemination events, engagement events, public communication events) are going to be fitted in these specially designed slides.

Figure 15: POIESIS branding as applied to the power point presentation.

3.4 POIESIS deliverable template

Figure 16 presents the deliverable template of POIESIS. Special emphasis has been put not only at providing a placeholder for all needed information, but also to produce an aesthetically appealing results, since almost all POIESIS deliverables are public. In this respect they are not going to play the role of purely technical reports, but also of additional means of dissemination and communication.

Figure 16: POIESIS branding, as applied to the deliverable template.

4 Deviations from DoA

There are no deviations from the DoA.